

STUDIES ON THE FORMATION OF DYES DERIVED FROM 8-OXYQUINOLINE ALDEHYDES AND FROM 2-OXYANTHRAQUINONE ALDEHYDE.

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Little investigations appear to have been made both on triphenylmethane as well as on pyronine dyes containing quinoline or anthraquinone nucleus. These dyes are of much interest on account of the presence of the condensed and heterocyclic ring systems. In the present paper some interesting pyronine and triphenylmethane dyes derived from 5- and 7-aldehyde-8-oxyquinoline and from 1-aldehyde-2-oxyanthraquinone have been described.

5-Aldehyde-8-oxyquinoline and 7-aldehyde-8-oxyquinoline were prepared by the action of chloroform on 8-oxyquinoline in presence of alkali, while the 1-aldehyde-2-oxyanthraquinone was prepared similarly from 2-oxy-anthraquinone (*cf.* Sen and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 17A). By the condensation of the quinoline aldehydes with dimethylaniline and also with resorcinol in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid as the condensing agent, dyes of triphenylmethane type have been obtained, the leuco-bases on oxidation with lead peroxide in the usual way give the corresponding carbinols. The condensation with *o*-cresotinic acid has been effected in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid. The leuco-base obtained, when oxidised with nitrosyl sulphate, dyes silk and wool a beautiful orange shade. The dimethylaniline compound dyes wool and silk, from dilute acetic acid bath, a deep blue shade, while the resorcin compound produces a magnificent golden yellow shade. Pyronine dyes have been obtained by condensing the aldehydes with diethyl *m*-aminophenol and with resorcinol in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid. The diethyl-*m*-amino compound produces a reddish violet shade on wool and silk, while the compound with resorcinol dyes silk and wool a delightful reddish orange shade. It is of interest to note that when the pyrone ring is not closed (*i.e.*, as in the condensation between the aldehyde and resorcinol in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid) silk and wool are dyed a golden yellow shade, while by closing the pyrone ring the colour is deepened to reddish orange.

1-Aldehyde-2-oxyanthraquinone has also been successfully condensed with (i) dimethylaniline, using hydrochloric acid as the condensing agent; (ii) *o*-cresotinic acid and (iii) diethyl *m*-aminophenol in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid. It has been noticed that the C=O groups in the

anthraquinone ring do not react in these condensations. The compound with dimethylaniline, on oxidation with lead peroxide, dyes silk a delightful bluish violet shade while a greenish blue shade is produced on wool. The diethyl-*m*-amino compound produces a reddish violet shade on wool and silk, while the compound with *o*-cresotinic acid, on oxidation with nitrosyl sulphate, dyes silk a light yellow and wool a deep yellow shade which changes to reddish shade by after-chroming.

As the methods of preparation and properties of the corresponding condensation products of 5- and 7-aldehydo-8-oxyquinolines are identical, only those of 7-aldehydo-8-oxyquinoline have been given in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL.

TABLE I.

Dyes derived from 7-aldehydo-8-oxyquinoline.

Condensation with	Procedure and analysis.
Dimethylaniline.	Aldehyde (2 g.) and dimethylaniline (5 c.c.) were heated on a boiling water-bath for 30 hours with frequent addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c. in all); the solution was made alkaline, distilled in steam, filtered and acidified with HCl and reprecipitated with ammonia. It crystallised from chloroform as a bluish green powder, m.p. 177°, yield 70%. It is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether; easily soluble in chloroform. The carbinol base dyes silk and wool a deep blue shade from dilute acetic acid bath (Found: N, 10.76. $C_{26}H_{27}ON_3$ requires N, 10.58 per cent).
Resorcinol.	Aldehyde (2 g.) and resorcinol (4 g.) were heated with concentrated HCl (10 c.c.) for 20 hours and treated in the same manner as above. The compound, precipitated with ammonia is a faint yellow powder. It crystallised from alcohol in black shining plates, m.p. 148°, yield theoretical. It is insoluble in water, ether and chloroform; sparingly soluble in acetone and acetic acid; moderately soluble in hot alcohol. The carbinol base dyes wool and silk a greenish yellow shade. (Found: N, 3.87. $C_{27}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 3.73 per cent).
<i>o</i> -Cresotinic acid	Aldehyde (2 g.) and <i>o</i> -cresotinic acid (2.5 g.) when stirred with concentrated sulphuric acid (12 g.) for 5 hours at room temp. gave a liquid product which was oxidised with nitrosyl sulphate in the usual way; the mixture poured into water and filtered. It is soluble in sodium bicarbonate and insoluble in most organic solvents. It is a yellowish powder, m.p. above 250°. It dyes wool and silk an orange shade.
Diethyl <i>m</i> -aminophenol.	Aldehyde (2 g.) and diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol (3 g.) when heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) in an oil-bath for 4 or 5 hours at 120-130° gave a product which was treated with water and filtered. The filtrate was basified with ammonia when a reddish violet powder was obtained. It crystallised from alcohol as a violet powder softening at 80°, yield 90%. It is easily soluble in alcohol (pink solution with slightly violet fluorescence); sparingly soluble in ether; insoluble in petroleum ether and chloroform. It dyes silk and wool a reddish violet shade. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{30}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 8.7 per cent).

Condensation with	Procedure and analysis.
Resorcinol in presence of H_2SO_4 .	A mixture of aldehyde (2 g.) and resorcinol (4 g.) when heated with concentrated H_2SO_4 in the usual manner yielded a reddish powder which crystallised from alcohol in black shining plates melting at $86-87^\circ$, yield theoretical. It is easily soluble in alcohol (orange-red solution with yellowish green fluorescence); soluble in alkali with green fluorescence. It dyes wool and silk an orange-red shade. (Found: N, 4.01. $C_{22}H_{15}O_6N$ requires N, 3.7 per cent).

TABLE II.

Dyes derived from 1-aldehyde-2-oxyanthraquinone.

Dimethylaniline.	A mixture of aldehyde (2 g.) and dimethylaniline (3 c.c.) when heated on a boiling water-bath with concentrated HCl (5 c.c.) and treated in the usual way gave a product which crystallised from alcohol as bluish green microcrystalline powder, m. p. 78° , yield 70%. It is insoluble in water and petroleum ether; sparingly soluble in alcohol and ether; moderately soluble in chloroform. The carbinol base dyes silk and wool a bluish violet shade. (Found: N, 5.8%. $C_{11}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.8 per cent).
Diethyl- <i>m</i> -aminophenol.	Aldehyde (2 g.) and diethyl <i>m</i> -aminophenol (3 g.) when heated with concentrated H_2SO_4 and treated subsequently as in the preceding compound gave a violet product which crystallised from dilute alcohol as a violet powder, m. p. 135° , yield 90%. It is insoluble in water; easily soluble in alcohol (pink), ether (yellow soln.), chloroform and acetone and insoluble in petroleum ether. It dyes wool and silk a reddish violet shade. (Found: N, 5.21. $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 4.99 per cent).
<i>o</i> -Cresotinic acid	The condensation was effected in the same manner as with 7-aldehyde-8-oxyquinoline. The product was a yellowish powder insoluble in most organic solvents hence it could not be purified for analysis. It dyes wool and silk a yellowish shade which becomes reddish on after-chroming.

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